

Kaleidophone – A Collaborative Web-based Tool for Comprovization Based on Arithmetic Operation Grammar

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***Abstract.** Kaleidophone corresponds in concept to a previous work which found its way into the article "Composing by Laypeople: A Broader Perspective Provided by Arithmetic Operation Grammar" (G. Kramann, Computer Music Journal 44(1):17-34) as THE FLIPPIN POMPOMS' but is web-based and is collaborative by means of the internet. As the preceding work, Kaleidophone has two successively connected transformation layers responsible for generating the currently sounding music. Special attention was paid to easy usability in order to give all participants the possibility to influence the musical performance themselves.*

1. Introduction

Kaleidophone has two successively connected transformation layers responsible for generating the currently sounding music. On the first layer, a multicolored spatial figure is designed. This figure is projected twice into the plane. The contiguous colored areas in these two 2D projections are each translated into an arithmetic formula. These two formulas represent the second transformation layer and henceforth represent a generation rule for the tone sequences of two software-based musical instruments. Since all participants in Kaleidophone are not only listeners, but should also have and use the opportunity to change into a role in which they actively influence the musical performance, Kaleidophone itself is available as a web page under the link <http://kramann.info/kaleidophone> and an introductory video into its use is given here: <https://youtu.be/HzZjTQTjJko>. The name Kaleidophone comes from a special visualization option that can be selected by means of the button "KALEIDOSCOPIIC VIEW (passive)" and that has a certain similarity with looking into a kaleidoscope.

2. How is collaboration organized on the web at Kaleidophone?

The only difference in using Kaleidophone between now, when you are reading this text, and a targeted collaborative performance at Ubiquitous Music 2021 is that more people will probably come together using it. Thus, Kaleidophone is not only ubiquitous in space but – due to its durability – also in time and is intended to contribute to "Everyday Creativity" (compare D.Keller et.al.: "Ubiquitous Music", pp.29-30, Springer, Heidelberg 2014) with a special focus on laypeople in particular. To ensure this, no registration is required on the start page. Only a nickname must be entered before the start. When the START button is pressed, the view changes to a display showing a 5 by 5 by 5 grid with colored spheres on the left and two 2D projections of this structure next to it. Still further

to the right, a piano roll-like representation depicts the musical structure currently being created. The data describing the current state of this structure and the angles at which the projections are made are continuously downloaded from a central server and thus updated. Conversely, any user can add or remove a colored sphere at any time. This action is then stored on the server and is available to all users after some time. There is only one simple rule how the actions of the different users are handled: Each location in the 3D grid and each angle is considered separately. If a change is made at a particular location by user A, it will only take effect if either the last change at that location was also made by user A, or the last change made by a user B at that location was at least 30 seconds ago. Sound generation takes place locally at each client. Only the structural data of the 3D shape and its projection angle are exchanged between the participants. This data exchange takes place via the HTTP protocol. Although this has the disadvantage that changes sometimes only take effect with a delay of several seconds at all clients, it has the advantage that Kaleidophone is constantly available in its full functionality and the data exchange works very securely.

3. How Does a Collaborative Comprovization with Kaleidophone Work in Practice?

Kaleidophone was programmed in Javascript and can be used at any time by navigating to the weblink <http://kramann.info/kaleidophone>. The piano roll displayed with each change reacts immediately and visualizes the musical structure over several bars. In particular, this allows participants to quickly assess the musical result of their changes and thus opens up the possibility of quickly searching the parameter space in order to then remain with an appealing setting. It is possible to arrange to perform at a certain time with each other. Basically, however, a change of the persons handling kaleidophone is fluently possible and the duration of a performance is in principle unlimited. To enhance the feeling of creating together, the nicknames of the currently active participants are displayed in the order of their activity.

4. What sense does it make, as in Kaleidophone, to unfold a musical structure across multiple hierarchical layers of representation?

The layers of representation used are borrowed from a context of meaning from the life-world (in the sense of Edmund Husserl's phenomenology, see e.g. E.Husserl, D.Carr [transl.]: "The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology", pp. 48-53, Northwestern University Press, Evanston 1970.) of the users, which is familiar to them: because of their own corporeality and the corporeality of the world around them, users already know what it means to form a spatial gestalt and to project it into the plane.

The use of arithmetic formulas as a function of time on the underlying level, which finally lead to the generation of the musical events, was similarly done with the intention of referring to a familiar context of meaning from the users' lifeworld.

The point is not so much to actually fully comprehend the context, but to provide a plausible, compact, easy to survey and manipulate symbolic representation for the currently audible musical structure. The basic idea overall is that a comprehensible handling of Kaleidophone can be learned over time via the perception of the presented connection between figure and formulas on the one hand with the current sound events and their visualization as piano roll on the other hand.